

NOISE TESTING AND PREDICTION OF A 3-STAGE HIGH SPEED TURBINE FOR ULTRAFAN®

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ABSTRACT

A 3-stage High Speed Turbine (HST) has been noise tested in a transonic and rotating wind tunnel facility located in Centro de Tecnologías Aeronáuticas (CTA) in Bilbao, Spain. Turbine design characteristics and measured conditions are fully representative of an Intermediate Pressure Turbine (IPT) powering the future Rolls-Royce family of UltraFan® engines. Analysis is focused in experimentally characterize the different tonal and broadband acoustic sources generated and technologies for noise suppression. In particular, blade and vane indexing or clocking. Prediction capability is investigated as well by the comparison of measurements with a set of semi-empirical, semi-analytical and numerical methods.

Keywords: Noise, UltraFan, Turbine, Aeroacoustics

NOMENCLATURE

B	Number of blades
CTA	Centro de Tecnologías Aeronáuticas
GPU	Graphic Processing Units
IPT	Intermediate Pressure Turbine
ITP	Industria de Turbo Propulsores
MPI	Message Passing Interface
$\text{Mu}^2\text{s}^2\text{T}$	Multirow Unsteady Unstructured Specific Solver for Turbomachinery
NMM	Noise Measurement Module
OAC	Optimized Acoustic Coupling
OGV	Outlet Guide Vane
PWL	sound PoWer Level
RANS	Reynolds-Averaged Navier-Stokes
RMD	Radial Mode Decomposition
SPL	Sound Pressure Level
TURN0	TURbine NOise prediction tool
UNRBC	Unsteady Non-Reflecting Boundary Conditions
V	Number of Vanes
XIPTY	X^{th} stage Blade Passing Frequency coming from Y^{th} Intermediate Turbine Stage

1. INTRODUCTION

Turbine noise can be an important contributor to the overall Aircraft perceived noise levels, being Arrivals where this component is typically more relevant [1]. Noise sources are commonly controlled by a smart selection of blade and vane counts through the different stages of the turbine and the use of acoustic treatment in the hot nacelle.

Continuous efforts for designing greener and quieter engines makes necessary the use of alternative noise reduction technologies beyond the above-mentioned practices. This is particularly relevant for the future generation of the Rolls-Royce UltraFan® engines, where a gearbox is introduced between the low speed fan and the Intermediate Pressure Turbine (IPT), making the noise sources of the latter increase referred to the equivalent Direct Drive engines [2].

ITP Aero has been working during the last years in a set of technology developments aimed to understand, predict and reduce noise levels emanating from High Speed Turbines, including development of semi-analytical and numerical methods, physical understanding, testing prototypes and noise reduction technologies [3][4][5][6]. In this context, a full 3-stage IP Turbine has been designed accounting aerodynamic, mechanic and acoustic trade-offs, being completely equivalent of an engine design module. Regarding noise technologies, rear stages does have the Optimized Acoustic Coupling (OAC) technology for reducing tone energy by choosing appropriate vane shapes and repeating blade and vane counts in stages 2 and 3. OAC has been investigated during last years and noise benefits demonstrated in turbine part rigs [3][4].

Full 3-stage IP Turbine rig includes the Outlet Guide Vane (OGV) row and aerodynamic measured results have confirmed to be aligned with target and prediction capability [7]. The purpose here is to analyze the equivalent for noise.

To start with, Experimental Set-up and Methods are described with particular focus on measuring and predicting acoustics. Then, experimental results are presented for Landing representative working conditions and split in the various tonal and broadband noise source mechanisms. To finish with, prediction and measurements are compared concluding on overall noise objectives and prediction capability assessment.

2. EXPERIMENTAL SET-UP AND METHODS

This section describes the facility in which noise measurements have been taken, vehicle main characteristics and testing procedure.

Prediction is focused on tones, internally generated broadband and tone broadening when tones interacts with high levels of turbulence. A set of semi-analytical, semi-empirical and numerical methods summarized in Table 1 are considered and highlighted in this section.

	TONES	BROADBAND	TOE BROADENING
Fast (Semi-empirical)			
Higher Fidelity (Semi-Analytical)		Orpheus	
CFD (Numerical)			

Table 1. Prediction Methods Summary

2.1 Facility Description

Experiments described in this paper have been conducted in the transonic and rotating turbine testing facility at the CTA (Centro de Tecnologías Aeronáuticas), in Zamudio, Spain. The facility consists of a continuous flow, open circuit, variable density wind tunnel, where Reynolds and Mach numbers can be adjusted independently. A two-stage compressor group is employed upstream of the working section, with a maximum delivery pressure of 450 kPa for a mass flow rate of 18 kg/s. By cooling the airflow downstream of both compressor stages (the facility allows for both inter- and after-cooling), the inlet temperature to the working section can also be set independently. In addition, a heat exchanger is utilized between the exhaust and the working section inlet to further rise the temperature of the latter. Inlet total temperatures over 500 K are thus possible.

Pressures downstream of the working section are adjusted by the operation of two vacuum pumps, which allow for a minimum outlet sub-atmospheric pressure of 12 kPa. The facility was described in detail by Vázquez et al [8].

2.2 Test Vehicle

It consists of a three-stage intermediate pressure turbine (IPT), representative of Ultrafan® IPT, including a final row of highly twisted OGVs. The rig was described in detail by Torre et al [7]. Figure 1 shows a schematic of the turbine.

Figure 1. Schematic View of the Turbine

In terms of clocking, the number of vanes in Stages 2 and 3 is the same. The third stator has a positioning system that allows testing eight different equidistant circumferential positions over one pitch, hence the distance between two consecutive clocking positions is 12.5% of the stator pitch.

These circumferential positions can be adjusted from the outside of the turbine so changes between positions can be made easily. This system, in addition to the circumferential position, also ensures the axial position of the stator for each circumferential position change. Figure 2 shows a picture of the stator 3 positioning system.

Figure 2. Stator 3 Positioning System

2.3 Testing Procedure

Noise is acquired by the Noise Measurement Module (NMM) located downstream the turbine. This device is able to rotate 360° and the instantaneous tangential position is known with an uncertainty of less than 0.1 degrees.

The NMM consists of two static casings and a rotating one. In the static casing at the output part of the module, a liner is installed in order to attenuate noise and unwanted frequencies during aeroacoustics measurements. The module motion control is performed by a servomotor, which has an encoder that is measured in synchronization with the acquisition of the instrumentation data to know the instantaneous position of the module.

The sweeps are carried out automatically by means of a software where a table of movements is programmed including different speeds, stops and triggers. This control system is

synchronized with the probes radial actuator system and the data acquisition system.

All the instrumentation in the module is mounted on strips to give versatility to the assembly. Figure 3 shows a picture of the module.

Figure 3. Noise Measurement Module (NMM)

Two of these strips with 168° between are instrumented for Kulite pressure transducers to perform aeroacoustics measurements. Each strip covers all the axial length of the rotating casing so that 23 Kulite transducers are mounted on each strip with a specific axial distribution for an optimum modal decomposition. This is for maximizing the outcomes from the Radial Mode Decomposition (RMD) [9].

Besides the rotating transducers, 10 non-rotating microphones are located at different locations aimed to support the RMD process [10] and to check facility sources.

Prior to the noise campaign, an aerodynamic campaign was performed to characterize the rig in terms of aerodynamics (turbine performance, stator wakes). The noise measurements were taken in absence of any aerodynamic instrumentation such rakes or aerodynamic probes between the turbine rig and the NMM.

2.3 Numerical Methods

Steady and linear unsteady simulations presented in this work are performed with Mu^2s^2T , a suite of CFD codes property of ITP Aero. It is the recommended tool for aerodynamics, aeroelasticity and aeroacoustics in the design of ITP Aero products with demonstrated capability [1][11][12][13][14]. The spatial domain is discretized via hybrid unstructured grids and the fluxes computation is performed via an edge data structure. Time-marching technique with an explicit five-stage Runge-Kutta is used, with Multigrid [11] to accelerate convergence and Message Passing Interface (MPI). Mu^2s^2T is able to run in Graphic Processing Units (GPUs) [15].

Linear version of Mu^2s^2T is capable of performing single-row and multi-row multi-frequency noise simulations with 3D Unsteady Non-Reflecting Boundary Conditions (3DUNRBC) at

every inlet/outlet of each domain. Pre-/post-processing of the solutions is made with RECKONER, an in-house tool for post-processing the unsteady field based on a viscous linear formulation for radially varying swirling flows [16][17].

Linear simulations of the tonal noise coming from the different IPT stages have been performed at different operating conditions. Given that the number-off for stages 2 and 3 is the same, the first temporal harmonic of the tone coming from these stages is labeled as 1IPT2/3. For stage 1, the 1BPF is labeled as 1IPT1. For each interaction contributing to these tones, generation mechanisms for stator-rotor or rotor-stator interactions are run separately in single row linear simulations. The perturbations generated in each of these simulations are then introduced in a multi-row (it includes all the rows except the OGV) multi-frequency (several interaction modes are generated) computation that solves the multiple reflections between rows extracting the unsteady field along the turbine and the noise levels for the modes of interest at the OGV inlet. The transmission and scattering through the OGV is solved in a separate linear single row simulation.

Figure 4. Schematic view of V1-B1-V2 rows (left) and V2-B2-V3-B3 rows (right).

Aerodynamic grids, used for the calculation of the steady or base flow, are combined with noise grids, which have higher density of nodes and are dimensioned based on the smallest wavelength of interest for both tones in each of the rows. The grids are structured in radial direction with stretching near the walls and hybrid structured (boundary layer) – unstructured (inviscid area) in the blade-to-blade or 2D grid. A schematic view of the domain used is seen in Figure 4. Rows involved in the generation of 1IPT1 are seen in Figure 4-left, whereas the two last stages responsible of generating 1IPT2/3 tone are seen in Figure 4-right. The rotor-count for these two stages is the same, as well as the stator-count. Optimized vane shape introduced to the vanes in order to maximize clocking (optimized acoustic coupling) is clearly observed in the figure.

2.4 Semi-Empirical and Semi-Analytical Methods

Early stage predictions come from a semi-analytical tool for predicting turbine noise signature in aeroengines. TURNO is divided in different modules. It starts with estimating aerodynamics at different engine working conditions, then tones and broadband levels, liner attenuation, interaction with high levels of turbulence (tone broadening or ‘haystacking’), ultimately propagation effects and noise metrics computation.

Regarding tone and broadband noise estimation, TURNO accounts for a set of wake velocity, potential and turbulence sources that are estimated for a prescribed aerodynamic flow and losses. Unsteady model used is an extension of the Actuator Disk Theory for swirling flows as described in Escribano [18]. Spectral broadening model is based on time delay variations as proposed in Sijtsma et al [19]. TURNO has demonstrated capability for predicting tone noise with a discrepancy kept lower than 10 dB, as expected with this kind of semi-analytical tools [20].

Semi-analytical turbine broadband noise predictions are computed using the in-house tool, *Orpheus*, which is a frequency-domain RANS informed method validated against fan and turbine rigs. It combines a turbulence model based on Nallasamy's work [21] with an unsteady response model developed from Whitehead's flat plate cascade model [22][23] to model broadband wake interaction. The code is parallelized to be run on different control processing units (CPUs). Geometric, aerodynamics and turbulence inputs are obtained from a multi-row RANS simulation at several span positions to account for radial non-uniformities. Rotor tip clearances have not been included in the models for simplicity. In Figure 5, a turbine RANS solution is shown. Turbulence intensity and length scale are extracted at each row outlet plane. Geometric and aerodynamic parameters are obtained at the nine strips along the span where broadband predictions are computed. All strips are averaged to derive total SPL levels.

More information about the code and how its predictions compare with other state-of-the-art broadband noise prediction tools, as well as the impact that the RANS simulation may have on the results, can be found in the literature [24] [25] [26].

Figure 5. RANS solution ready to extract inputs for Orpheus

Three isotropic frequency-domain turbulence models are extensively used to make fan broadband noise predictions: Liepmann [27], von Kármán [28] and Gaussian [28]. In the absence of models specific for turbines, the three models can derive broadband noise predictions with *Orpheus*.

3. RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

Analysis starts with experimentally characterization of main source mechanisms measured, then prediction capability is investigated for tone noise coming from the front and rear part, and finally broadband coming whether from wake turbulence or tone broadening.

Figure 6. Circumferential and Axial Averaged SPL for an Approach representative condition and two clocking positions.

3.1 Experimental Analysis

Figure 6 shows circumferentially and axially averaged SPL in the NMM for the same Approach representative working condition measured in different days and different clocking positions. Stator 2 to stator 3 relative position influences mainly noise generation from stages 2 and 3 (1IPT2/3 tone) and with little influence on noise generated in in the front part tone. Besides, broadband energy around those tones with more clocking sensitivity changes accordingly. This suggest this amount of broadband energy comes from the interaction of the turbine tone and turbulence, similarly as the tone broadening effect observed in some wind tunnels [19].

Figure 7. 1IPT1 measured clocking sensitivity at Approach representative condition

Figure 8. 1IPT2/3 measured clocking sensitivity at Approach representative condition

Figure 9. Measured broadband noise modal decomposition for an Approach representative condition.

Figure 7 and Figure 8 show the clocking sensitivity for front (1IPT1) and rear (1IPT2/3) tones for the same working condition as shown in Figure 6. Each of the eight clocking position have been measured in different testing days and Clock 3 position is measured at the beginning and end of the test campaign for assessing repeatability. Acoustic Power (PWL) of the overall tone (SUM) is shown together with all the identified interaction mechanisms for each tone according to the Tyler & Sofrin [29]. B2/3-V2/3 and B2/3-2V2/3 contributing to the rear tone presents clocking sensitivities of around 10 dB and suggest a clear Stator 3 position role in the noise generation process. There are other mechanisms such as B1-V1-V2/3 in the front tone that show small clocking sensitivity, suggesting that

is Stator 2 rather Stator 3 the row implied in the generation process.

Figure 10. Circumferential and Axial Averaged SPL for an Approach representative condition, two clocking positions and including broadband source breakdown

Figure 9 shows the broadband modal decomposition at an Approach representative working condition. Measured broadband comes from the facility at low frequencies, internally generated turbine broadband source in the mid-high frequency range and tones interacting with turbulence within the turbine. Cut-on region is almost symmetrical with the spinning mode suggesting swirling flow downstream the OGV is low. Broadband modal decomposition together with experimental diagnostic analysis as those shown in [30] allows the estimation of facility, internally generated broadband and tone broadening as shown in Figure 10.

Figure 11. Front tone source breakdown as predicted by TURNO, CFD in comparison with measurements

3.2 Front Tone Analysis

First Vane of the turbine has low count, low aspect ratio and small distance to the first rotor located downstream. These characteristics makes the emergence of various noise sources coming from different first vane wake harmonics together with additional vortical and acoustic scattering phenomena through

Second Vane. More details of those physical mechanisms can be followed in [4].

Figure 12. Measured (solid lines) and predicted (symbols) IPT1 OGV scattering

Figure 11 shows up to ten mechanisms contributing to front tone according to the semi-analytical (TURNO, left), numerical (CFD μ^2s^2T , middle) and Measurements (right). Three of them are low count Vane 1 interacting with downstream Blade 1. Another two corresponds to Blade 1 interacting with downstream Vane 2. The other five mechanism implies the presence and interaction between Vane 1, Blade 1 and Vane 2. Both prediction methods and measurements agrees on the three-row mechanisms dominance over the two-row once. TURNO predicts overall energy with discrepancies lower than 10 dB, aligned with previous comparisons [20], but increased when looking at some of the individual mechanisms. CFD shows improved accuracy regarding overall energy and relative contribution of the ten mechanisms, something expected from a higher fidelity numerical method.

Tone sources as being transmitted through the OGV are scattered into various modes according to the Tyler & Sofrin [29] rule, resulting a mode pattern for the front tone as shown in Figure 12 for the same Approach representative working condition as in Figure 11. Both measurements (solid lines) and μ^2s^2T (symbols) agrees on the dominant spinning modes. Measurements shows high levels of the so-called steady distortion noise that is not predicted in the CFD.

3.3 Rear Tone Analysis

Figure 13 shows equivalent results than those in Figure 11 but for the rear tones coming from Stages 2 y 3. Here, interaction between Vane 2 and/or 3 with Blade 2 and/or 3 is the dominant source in both predictions and measurements. As for the front tone, numerical method presents better accuracy than TURNO although this latter remains as expected for a preliminary method. First Vane wakes are able to reach rear stages and produce sources of noise of around 10dB lower than the dominant (adjacent) ones. Those sources are not numerically simulated for computational saving reasons although TURNO is

able to predict some of those mechanisms even better than the dominant (adjacent) ones.

Figure 13. Rear tone source breakdown as predicted by TURNO, CFD in comparison with measurements

Figure 14. Measured (left) and predicted (right) clocking sensitivity of IPT2/3 at Approach representative condition.

Figure 14 shows the clocking sensitivity measured (left) and predicted (right) for Approach representative condition. The sound power level for the tone and for the dominant circumferential mode is shown, as well as the split in radial modes contributing to that dominant mode. The design clocking position, called CK4, is demonstrated to be beneficial for noise and close to be the optimum based on the measurements (less than 5% discrepancy). CK0 represents the worst position. The benefit predicted and measured is also in agreement for the tone, with more discrepancies for the dominant spinning mode, probably due to differences in the OGV scattering predicted and measured. The radial content of this dominant mode is in line with the measurements, with a first radial mode dominating with lower sensitivity than measured but similar optimum position around 60-70%. The predicted importance and sensitivity for the second radial mode is similar to the measurements, with higher discrepancies for the third radial order.

Regarding OGV scattering results and prediction capability, Figure 15 shows PWL levels for the various spinning modes contributing to the overall rear tone energy for two clocking positions and the same Approach representative working condition shown in Figure 13. Results shows clocking influences mainly interaction mode and the corresponding OGV

scatters but not secondary sources and/or distortion. Both measurements and CFD agrees in clocking depends on the scatter mode as well. That implies than, when the turbine is in an engine, clocking dependent modal pattern will behave differently whe transmisted through the nozzle downstream or radiated to the far-field.

Figure 15. Measured (solid lines) and predicted (symbols) 1IPT2/3 OGV scattering for two clocking positions

Figure 17. Liepmann broadband noise prediction breakdown when there are high turbulence levels within the turbine

Figure 16. Measured vs predicted broadband noise when there are high turbulence levels within the turbine

Figure 18. TURNO predicted internally generated broadband and tone broadening.

3.4 Broadband Analysis

Figure 16 shows measured and *Orpheus* predicted SPL levels for an Approach representative working condition. Trends linked to the frequency-domain turbulence models are observed even though the Gaussian model provides the most remarkable differences in the low-to-mid-frequency range (up to 4 dB).

It has to be noted that the noise coming from the tone broadening has not been simulated in *Orpheus*, and the prediction only accounts for turbine interaction broadband noise. Still, the predictions agree with the experimental sources split shown in Figure 10.

One of the advantages of using *Orpheus* is that every interaction source is computed and transmitted through the turbine until the outlet plane is reached. This makes it possible to identify the dominant sources and how they change as the operating point is changed.

Sources breakdowns are shown for the Approach representative working condition in Figure 17. It can be noticed that the balance between the sources can significantly change and that the final figure depends on the generation level but also the attenuation it suffers as it moves through the turbine. In general, the last rotor wake interacting with the OGV seems to be a less important source. This behavior has been already observed in other tonal [31] and broadband noise [24] studies.

Regarding TURNO capability for predicting broadband, Figure 18 shows the same measured results as in Figure 16 and Figure 17 with the semi-empirical turbulent interaction related source and that coming from spectral broadening. Regarding internally generated broadband, both amplitude and shape does

not differ much than Orpheus. This will not be the general case when looking at other vehicles and/or conditions where TURNO broadband prediction capability is generally similar of that for the tones and representative of a semi-empirical fast method. Regarding spectral broadening, prediction shown in *Figure 18* does not account tone over-prediction observed in *Figure 11* and *Figure 13*, but assuming tone noise is accurately predicted looking at measurements so that spectral broadening prediction capability can be assessed isolately.

4. CONCLUSION

The experimental characterization of the tonal and broadband noise sources of a 3-stage High Speed Turbine (HST) representative of UltraFan® has been presented. Tonal noise coming from forward part is dominated by the low aspect ratio first vane wake harmonics interacting with adjacent and non-adjacent rows, due to high order harmonics capability to generate noise when interacting with downstream rows. Rear stages designed in cut-on at approach representative conditions combine lean vanes and clocking in order to reduce noise via Optimized Acoustic Coupling (OAC) technology. Noise benefits and optimum positions for noise are identified, demonstrating the capability of this technology to reduce noise emissions in HSTs. The inclusion of the Outlet Guide Vane (OGV) in the prototype has allowed investigating the role of this component in noise generation and transmission, given the particularities of the detached flow at approach in these HSTs.

Comparison with predictions using semi-empirical, semi-analytical and numerical methods has demonstrated ITP in-house tools capability to predict IPT noise sources. Numerical methods, using tool Mu2s2t, are used to predict tonal sources coming from the forward and rear part of the turbine, as well as the benefits from the OAC technology. Optimum position predicted during pre-test stage is in agreement with the measurements, demonstrating the capability of numerical methods to estimate also the benefits of the technology during design stages. Regarding semi-empirical methods, Orpheus tool has been demonstrated a good alternative to numerical methods in order to avoid running millions of simulations with high computational cost. Orpheus predict internally generated broadband noise level in consistency with measurements, as well as supplying other information of interest as the identification of the dominant turbulence-row interactions. Semi-empirical methods are fast and reliable for preliminary design stages, with the capability of predicting tonal and broadband sources, as well as tone broadening effect occurring in turbulence dominated regions. Difficulties of this tool to predict tonal sources from low aspect ratio vanes and limitations to be used to predict OAC benefits has been shown in this work. On the contrary, broadband sources predicted are in fair agreement with measurements, being especially remarkable its capability to predict the tone broadening occurring in the OGV.

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